

Supplementary Ethics Statement

Ethical Considerations and Data Access in Ethnographic Fieldwork at Dazu and Anyue

This supplementary statement outlines the ethical considerations underpinning the ethnographic fieldwork conducted at the Dazu Rock Carvings and the Fengmen Temple in Anyue, China, and provides a rationale for the decision not to make interview transcripts publicly accessible.

Ethical Framework and Approval

The research was conducted under ethical approval from both institutions where the researcher was based during the study. Ethical clearance was granted following detailed review of research design, consent procedures, data management strategies, and potential participant risks. Ethical guidance has been consistently informed by the frameworks set out in the UK's **General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)** and by field-specific codes of practice in archaeology and anthropology.

The fieldwork, conducted in 2018 and 2023, employed **semi-structured interviews** and **participant observation** as part of a rapid ethnographic methodology. Participants included a wide range of stakeholders, including heritage professionals, local caretakers, site employees, tourists, and religious practitioners. Interviews typically took place one-on-one, with some joint interviews, and were conducted in settings that respondents found comfortable and familiar, including tea/coffee houses, homes, and public areas. No research was conducted with children or recognised vulnerable groups.

In addition to in-person interviews, follow-up interviews in 2023 were conducted via WeChat video calls, reflecting the evolving modalities of digital ethnographic engagement. Data gathering was guided by the principle of minimising harm and respecting local expectations around privacy, sacred space, and institutional sensitivity, particularly in the Chinese context where heritage conservation is closely linked to governance structures.

Contextual Norms and Confidentiality

It was determined at the outset of the project – during the design and ethics approval stages – that interview transcripts would not be made publicly available. This decision was based on a range of ethical, legal, and cultural considerations specific to the fieldwork context.

In mainland China, it is not common practice for ethnographic datasets involving human subjects to be made publicly accessible, especially when those interviews concern sensitive subjects such as the governance of heritage, institutional responsibility, and public sentiment regarding conservation practice. China's cultural heritage is a deeply politicised and symbolically charged field, and participants may not feel free to speak openly if they believe their responses could be disseminated outside their immediate context. Even anonymised transcripts, in small-scale heritage communities, may be traceable to specific individuals due to their roles or unique perspectives.

Furthermore, it is widely recognised among scholars conducting ethnographic research in China that written consent forms are often perceived by participants as formal, unfamiliar, or alienating. In many local settings, trust is built through relationships and oral agreements. Requiring written consent could therefore have undermined rapport, reduced participation, and, paradoxically, compromised the ethical integrity of the research by introducing discomfort or distrust. In keeping with best practices in Chinese ethnographic contexts, oral informed consent was obtained in all cases, and participants were reminded of their right to withdraw or decline to answer questions at any stage.

Participants were informed of how their data would be handled, the scope of the project, and the intended outcomes. Particular care was taken in handling sensitive topics, especially those involving perceptions of religious icons, state authority, or institutional legitimacy. The research was conducted with cultural respect, recognising that local values may not align neatly with externally defined academic or conservationist standards.

Anonymisation, Security, and Use of Data

All data have been stored securely and handled in accordance with data protection regulations. Identifiable personal information is stored separately from research content. Direct quotations used in the final research outputs have been carefully anonymised unless the participant explicitly requested attribution. Sensitive data with potential to impact community relations or institutional dynamics have been excluded from publication.

Given the impossibility of guaranteeing full anonymity in tightly knit communities, and in the absence of written consent for open archiving, the original interview data have not been deposited in public repositories. This is consistent with common practice in ethnographic research that prioritises participant wellbeing and aligns with guidelines from professional bodies such as the American Anthropological Association and the Association of Social Anthropologists of the UK.

Respecting Reciprocity and Social Norms

Finally, this project was designed with attention to reciprocity and fair return. Participants were offered small tokens of appreciation, meals, or other context-appropriate forms of recognition. The research design also prioritised low-impact engagement, allowing participants to choose times and spaces that suited them, and ensuring that participation did not entail economic or social cost.

While transcripts cannot be shared, the researcher remains committed to communicating findings to participants in accessible ways and to maintaining ethical obligations to the communities who contributed to the research.